

FEATURES OF SPEECH THERAPY FOR PEOPLE WITH DYSPHAGIA**Charchyan Anna**

PhD, lecturer

Faculty of Special and Inclusive Education ASPU Kh. Abovyan

annacharchyan@yahoo.com, +374 938117 23

Baghdasaryan Tatevik

Master of Faculty of Special and Inclusive Education

ASPU Kh. Abovyan

Speech therapist, "Child and Family Support Center" NGO

tatevik.baghdasaryan@list.ru, +374 94606973

Balabekyan Lida

Applicant of Chair of Special Pedagogy and Psychology

ASPU Kh. Abovyan

Speech therapist of "Yerazi Tun" rehabilitation center

balabekyan.lida@mail.ru, +374 94909815

Abstract. *The article presents cases of dysphagia in people with disorders of the nervous system due to diseases of various organ systems, gastrointestinal tract, tumors, etc. At different ages and due to different situations, a person may encounter neurodegenerative diseases, cerebral palsy, dementia, cerebral palsy (CI) accompanied by dysphagia. Dysphagia is characterized by difficulty or inability to swallow. According to a number of researchers, in adults it is mainly observed after cerebral palsy, and in children, in parallel with cerebral palsy, rhinolalia as a secondary disorder. There are few rehabilitation centers in Armenia where the work with dysphagia can be carried out with a complex medical, psycho-pedagogical approach and speech therapy. This is due to the fact that not all speech therapists*

can perform correct speech therapy intervention among persons with dysphagia, especially children. The results of our researches, as well as the lack of Armenian language literature, the incomplete awareness and training of specialists prove that the demand for clinical speech therapists in our country is quite high. The main specialists working with people with dysphagia are neurologists and speech therapists trained in various programs who are able to perform quality work.

As an example, experts invited from different countries of the world worked to overcome the dysphagia caused by the injuries of the soldiers who participated in the Artsakh wars. This circumstance gave us the opportunity to see the work of foreign specialists and cooperate with them. Our meetings and discussions with French-Armenian specialists allowed us to conclude that dysphagia in our country, unlike in European countries, occurs more often in children with cerebral palsy. The aim of our studies is to analyze the typical difficulties of persons with dysphagia, to present the features of the speech therapy work carried out with them during the rehabilitation work. We have studied and analyzed the practical experience of a number of foreign specialists, and combining it with the Armenian experience, we have presented a summary of the speech therapy work carried out with dysphagia in Armenia.

Keywords and phrases: *dysphagia, swallowing act, speech therapy, cerebral palsy of children (CPC), regulation of breathing and voice, speech therapy massage.*

INTRODUCTION. In recent years, the number of people with disorders of the nervous system has increased due to diseases of various organ systems, gastrointestinal tract, tumors, etc. At different ages and due to different situations, a person may encounter neurodegenerative diseases, cerebral palsy, dementia, cerebral palsy of children (CPC) accompanied by dysphagia. *Dysphagia* is characterized by difficulty or inability to swallow. According to a number of researchers, it is mainly observed in adults after cerebral palsy, and in children along with cerebral palsy,

rhinolalia, as a secondary disorder (Linievski Yu. V., Lineskaya K.Yu., Voronin K.A., 2008).

FUNDAMENTAL ISSUES: There are few rehabilitation centers in Armenia, where therapy with people with dysphagia can be carried out with a complex medical, psycho-pedagogical approach and from a speech therapy point of view. This is conditioned by the fact that not all speech therapists can perform correct speech therapy intervention among persons with dysphagia, especially children. The results of our conducted researches, as well as the lack of literature in Armenian, incomplete awareness and training of specialists prove that the demand for clinical speech therapists in our country is quite high.

The main specialists working with people with dysphagia are neurologists and speech therapists trained in various programs who are able to perform quality work. As an example, experts invited from different countries of the world worked to overcome the dysphagia caused by the injuries of the soldiers who took part in the Artsakh wars (in 2016 and 2020). This circumstance gave us an opportunity to follow the work of foreign specialists and to cooperate with them. Our meetings and discussions with French-Armenian specialists allowed us to conclude that dysphagia in our country, unlike European countries, occurs more often in children with cerebral palsy.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY: The objective of these studies is to analyze the typical difficulties of people with dysphagia, to present the features of the speech therapy work carried out with them during the rehabilitation work. We have studied and analyzed the practical experience of a number of foreign specialists, and by combining it with the Armenian experience, we have presented a summary of the speech therapy carried out with people having dysphagia in Armenia. We have analyzed the results of the research and presented them in percentage terms in this article. Directions for the organization of speech therapy process with persons with dysphagia, a number of methodological approaches, which will contribute to the effective organization of the work of specialists, have been presented.

ESSENCE OF THE STUDY

Dysphagia is a disorder of eating, swallowing, which is diagnosed in both adults and children. It is performed by a strong cough syndrome, salivation and difficulty in passing food to the throat [6, p. 5]. Disturbance of swallowing is one of the symptoms of many diseases, it is a sequence of coordinated, voluntary and involuntary (reflective) movements that ensures the movement of the content in the oral cavity to the esophagus and stomach [7, p. 9].

Dysphagia has a negative impact on a person's quality of life: it leads to complications of the respiratory system, becomes a cause of dehydration, metabolic disorders, cachexia and disability [7]; [8].

According to the French physiologist F. Dysphagia dysphagia is one of the most common sequelae of cerebral palsy, a traumatic brain injury. Along with dysphagia, there is a feature of the patient's psychological state, up to the development of a severe depressive state. In the case of dysphagia, the early start of rehabilitation work reduces as much as possible the risk of developing further complications: aspiration pneumonia, metabolic disorder, malnutrition, weakness-exhaustion, death [7, p. 8]. Dysphagia is diagnosed when the centers responsible for swallowing are disturbed. According to professional literature, 60% of patients after cerebral palsy have spasticity of frontal muscles, tongue, throat or esophagus. When liquid or food particles enter the respiratory system, complications arise not only for nutrition, but also for preventing aspiration pneumonia [6]; [3]. As a result, instead of actively recovering after a stroke, elder people face new problems. due to malnutrition and dehydration, the body's recovery potential is reduced, as there is a risk of airway obstruction. Disturbance of the functional interaction of the structures involved in the act of absorption causes the patient to eat poorly. Symptoms of neurogenic dysphagia may occur in case of sensory-motor nerve fiber dysfunction (J.R. Malagelada, F. Bazzoli, A. Elewaut A., 2004).

According to phonograph, phonoped specialist in voice disorders and their rehabilitation, Dr. A. A. Almazova (Almazova E. C. 1960), speech therapy work in dysphagia is organized in the following directions:

Regulation of breathing, the main purpose of which is to restore verbal breathing and coordinate the processes of breathing and voice production [4]; [6].

In the initial stage, **breathing exercises are performed** taking into account the severity of the patient's condition and the level of mental activity. E. F. Arkhipova, studying the speech therapy work carried out in the case of children with cerebral palsy, emphasized the regulation of breathing, which improves and activates the functional and self-regulating mechanisms of all organ systems. Below are some examples of breathing exercises:

- Blow and put out the candle /match/,
- Blow so that the flame of the candle/match/ waves, but does not go out,
- Blow and make soap bubbles,
- Blow through the wand to create bubbles in the water,
- Blow on the butterflies cut out of paper so that they move,
- Blow up the balloon, the paper petals to make it spin,
- Blowing to move the boat on the water, make waves on the water [2].
- etc.

Regulation of speech breathing. The main purpose of breathing exercises is to restore speech breathing and coordinate breathing and voice production processes [5];[6]. Breathing exercises were also suggested for (Rulle E.J.L., 1973).

1. Differentiation of nasal and oral breathing,
2. In order to form a prolonged exhalation under the control of the movements of the abdominal and abdominal muscles,
3. In order to develop the ability of uniform, rhythmic distribution of air while speaking [11].

According to E. V. Lavrova (Lavrova E.V., 1973) in case of dysphagia, the stages of implementation of speech therapy are the following:

- ❖ Selection of food type (selection of stability and degree of concentration of liquid and solid food) to ensure the energy requirement of the patient's body,
- ❖ Determining the correct position (creating conditions that facilitate the patient's food intake), feeding method and quantity,
- ❖ Stimulation of the sensitivity of the oral mucosa,
- ❖ Regulation of respiratory and vocal functions,
- ❖ Stimulation of absorption,
- ❖ Increase in the functional activity of the muscles involved in chewing and swallowing food: masticatory, facial and tongue muscles,
- ❖ Controlling the regular hygienic condition of the oral cavity,
- ❖ Providing information on feeding and oral hygiene to patients and their carers.

The next direction of the organization of speech therapy is the *implementation of voice exercises* aimed at the gradual activation and coordination of the neuromuscular apparatus of the larynx to restore the full voice process (Almazova E.S., 1960). E. S. Almazova suggests to take into account the following features when performing vocal exercises:

- **In case of hypo tonus**, activation of the muscles of the vocal apparatus,
- **In case of hyper tonus**, elimination of excess tension, restoration of voice leading kinesthesia (Lavrova E. V. 1973, Lavrova E. V., Taptapova S. L. 1984).

In order to prevent the strengthening of the pathological voice of patients and the occurrence of a neurotic reaction, voice rehabilitation should be started as early as possible [3]; [2]. Below are some examples of *exercises for voice regulation*:

- Inhale, exhale through the mouth + sound - similar to a loud yawn,
- Inhale, exhale through the mouth + vowel / a, o, u, etc./,
- Pronounce single vowels long and smoothly,
- A, O, U, E, I, Y,
- Pronounce long and fluent phonemes consisting of 2, 3, 4 vowels.

For example:

- AA, AA
- AOA, AAO, AOU, AOE
- AOA, AOOAOU, AOAOAO, AOOAOUAOU, AEAEAEAAE, AEOAEOAAEOAEO
- A - O, A-O, U-E, U-I....
- A-E-O, A-E-O, A-E-O.....
- A-e-o -i, a-E-o -i, a-e-o -i, a-e-o -I....

The next direction of organization of speech therapy is the *extra-verbal exercises and speech therapy massage*.

The main goal of speech therapy massage is: [2, page 7]

- to regulate the tone of the general, oral apparatus, facial muscles,
- to reduce the performance of hypo-dissolution and/or dissolution of the muscles of the oral apparatus,
- to reduce performance of pathological movements of the speech apparatus muscles (synkinesias, hyperkinesias, etc.),
- to stimulate proprioceptive senses,
- to improve the mobility of the reproductive organs,
- to activate the muscle groups of the peripheral speech apparatus,
- to form voluntary, coordinated movements of the oral organs.

Exercises aimed at swallowing regulation. In some cases, after a cerebral palsy, the patient's movement disorder may persist, which is quite an unpleasant feeling and worries the patient (Lavrova E.V., 1984). However, regular exercises aimed at strengthening the muscles that carry out swallowing action will help to improve and also completely restore the act of swallowing and avoid other interventions [3]; [4]. Among them are, for example, imitation of familiar movements:

- ✓ Coughing "Uh-Uh",
- ✓ Yawning with mouth wide open,

- ✓ Whistle without a sound, straining the oral cavity,
- ✓ Snoring,
- ✓ Imagine that there is food in the mouth, try to chew and swallow it,
- ✓ Pronounce the "*m*" sound as long as the exhaled air is sufficient.
- ✓ Sequential pronunciation of vowel sounds: "A, E, I, O, U".
- ✓ Sequentially pronounce the following sounds: "I-A", "I-A" (pronounce the sound "I" long and the sound "A" short),
 - ✓ Keep the water in the mouth, gradually changing the position of the head,
 - ✓ Pronunciation exercises.

E. F. Arkhipova who studies children's cerebral palsy and the disorders encountered in that case, suggested **oral and facial muscle exercises** from the point of view of regulating dysphagia

➤ Pronounce vowel sounds: *a, e, i* to activate the muscles of the soft palate. It is also recommended to pronounce the sounds *a, a, a, e, e, e, e, i, i, i* then *ae, ae, ae, ea, ea, ea, ai, ai, ai, ai, ai, ai* then *ae, ae, ae, ae* in a certain order.

- Raise eyebrows,
- Frowne eyebrows (get angry),
- Close eyes sequentially,
- Open and close eyes 3 times without interruption,
- Smile with closed mouth,
- Whistle,
- Show the upper teeth,
- Show the lower teeth,
- Smile so that both upper and lower teeth are visible,
- Blow and extinguish a lighted match,
- Rinse the mouth, moving the water from the right cheek to the left and vice versa, trying not to spill the water,
- Move air from one side of the mouth to the other,

➤ Round the lips by adopting the position of pronunciation of the “o” sound.

We conducted a survey among speech therapists and doctors regarding the specifics of work with people with dysphagia. Fifteen speech therapists, four oncologists, five neurologists participated in the survey from Yerevan "Erebuni" Medical Center, "Astghik" Medical Center, "Republican Children's Rehabilitation Center", "Yerazi Tun" Children's Rehabilitation Center, "Sors" Development and Day Care Center, as well as "Arabkir" Child Development and Rehabilitation Center of Artashat City and Aragatsotn from the "Kosh Children's Rehabilitation Center" institutions of Kosh region, Kosh community. As a result of our studies, we have found out that 50% of specialists were guided by an individual approach, 5% by the etiopathogenetic principle, 7% by a complex approach, 10% by accessibility, 15% by - the principle of a systematic approach, only 13% of speech therapists were guided by the principle of consistency and sequence.

It was also found out what kind of difficulties occur in working with people with dysphagia. The 5% of the specialists cited the presence of comorbidities as a difficulty, 10% cited the risk of aspiration, and another 10% cited the risk of patient suffocation. The 15% of the specialists who participated in the survey considered the age of the patient a difficulty and only 60% considered the patient's condition important in the context of the difficulty.

Diagram.1 Difficulties of speech therapy of people with dysphagia

The 5% of specialists mentioned that the change in voice is characteristic of people with dysphagia, 10% stated psychological fear, 10% identified salivation, 15% breathing difficulties, 15% chewing difficulties, 15% % - weight loss, and the remaining 20% reported lack of appetite as a feature.

Diagram 2. Characteristics of people with dysphagia according to survey results

While performing speech therapy in case of dysphagia, it is necessary to take into account a number of general and unique principles: individual approach, etiopathogenetic, complex approach, simplicity, systematic approach, development, account of the mutual connection of speech and other mental processes, as well as the principles of consistency. Analyzing the results of our studies, we present a number of tips for people with swallowing disorder, following which will simply facilitate the rehabilitation activities carried out by specialists:

- Eat and drink only while sitting, if it is impossible to raise the head of the bed at least by 30 degrees.
- Maintain an upright position after eating.
- Take food slowly and in small portions, slightly lowering the chin to the chest, it facilitates the act of swallowing.

- The basis of the diet should be dense drinks and food (fermented foods: kissel, jelly, mashed potatoes, cutlets, soufflé, etc.),
- It is forbidden to use all crispy foods (biscuits, cereal foods, nuts, etc.). It's easy to get choked by them.
- It is also not recommended to use meat and citrus fruits, because the fibers are very difficult to chew.
- It is not recommended to mix food and drinks. The patient can choose to drink before or after meals.
- After eating, make sure that there are no pieces of food left in the mouth, then rinse the mouth. If the patient is choking, he should be given the opportunity to cough. According to several authors, it is not recommended to drink at that time, because the liquid can easily enter the respiratory system (Evzelman M.A., 2006, Kogan O.G., Naidin V. L., 1988).

CONCLUSION: Our studies allow us to conclude that in most cases the lack of cooperation between specialists, the specialists' not fully understanding the problem and other issues often lead to a negative outcome. And as an observation, we can note that in order for specialists to be able to provide a timely and professional approach to people with speech disorders, it is necessary to develop the field of clinical speech therapy, prepare and train clinical speech therapists/neuro speech therapists. What will actually improve the condition of people with dysphagia, will overcome a number of these gaps, and will also contribute to the involvement of narrow specialists in the restoration of the swallowing act of people with dysphagia.

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